

**FROM DIVINE JUDGMENT TO INSTITUTIONAL FAILURE:
A READING OF HOSEA 8:4 IN THE CONTEXT OF
LEADERSHIP CRISIS IN NIGERIA**

By

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Abstract

This paper focused on leadership crisis and in approaching the problem, Hosea 8:4 was studied in view of contextualizing it to the Nigerian situation. The aim of this study was to establish the fact that Nigeria just like 8th century Israel was bedeviled by leadership crisis which led to its destruction and annihilation by the Assyrians. Nigeria is indeed groaning under intense leadership crisis and the nation is witnessing the disintegration of the structure of governance and moving towards being a failed state. This study adopted the historical-critical, contextual and comparative methods. It discovered that 8th century Israel was faced with coups and counter coups which led to instability and leadership crisis. It found out that Israel broke the covenantal principle with YHWH and engaged in religious and political apostasies. It discovered that all forms of injustices, oppression, foolish political alliances and the worshipping of idols took place in Israel. This study found out that the situation of 8th century Israel perfectly depicted Nigeria's present democratic state where leaders emerge through rigged electoral processes. It discovered that resources were wrongly managed, utilized and deployed for personal gains. Consequently, this paper discovered that leadership crisis is the root cause of the economic, security, health, educational, etc. crisis faced by Nigerians. It concluded by recommending that there is need for a return to basic moral and ethical principles of doing what is right in terms of leadership for the situation to change.

Keyword: Leadership crisis, Electoral malpractice, Development, Corruption, Economy

Introduction

The human person is essentially a political being and in this wise, the question of leadership, authority and legitimacy of leaders are always at the heart of all conversations in societies or communities where humans exist. Humans would always seek for leadership positions and this desire to lead, is not only natural but is geared always to ensuring stability, orderliness, organization, development, prosperity and general well-being of the members of the society. In this same vein, it should be stressed that leadership could be for manipulation, domination and oppression of the members of a society or community. Leadership is a complex phenomenon and it embodies the totality of the will of the people, who submit their will and sovereignty to a chosen leader who in turn is expected to ensure the economic well-being of the citizens, provides protection for the lives and properties of the citizens, protects the rights, dignity of the people and guarantee the attainment of the positive self -aspirations of the people.

The indictment of the political leaders in Hosea's time is greatly connected to the depraved or diseased nature of the monarchy during his time. In other words, the northern kingdom which was characterized by palace coups and counter coups leading to the reigns of usurpers and many ignominious murders. That is, the question of leadership and legitimacy was a big deal in the northern kingdom during the 8th century BC and obviously, this set the stage for massive leadership crisis which resulted to the total collapse of government structure and brought about hardship, misery and pain to the citizens of the northern kingdom of Israel.

Similarly, the quest for leadership position in Nigeria is one that is highly coveted and indeed elections into these positions are messy in some cases. Elections in Nigeria are fraught with criminal irregularities which include: killing of voters or electorates, snatching of ballot boxes, voter's intimidation, vote buying and inducements, inducement of the electoral umpire and its officials and the use of state apparatus to subvert the will of the people. This surely has led to the emergence of incompetent and unprepared persons into leadership positions and is responsible for the massive leadership crisis Nigeria is facing. Consequently, this

paper is an attempt to study leadership crisis in Nigeria. To achieve this goal, Hosea 8:4 which provides a biblical context of leadership crisis in 8th century Israel is studied. Basically, this paper argues that just like Hosea 8:4 presented leadership crisis in ancient Israel, Nigeria too is faced with unprecedented leadership crisis leading to economic, political, social, human etc. failures.

Background to the Text of Hosea 8:4

Hosea began his prophetic ministry during the prosperous and military success of both Israel and Judah (cf. 2 Kings 14:25-28; 2 Chron 26:2, 6:15) in the first half of the 8th century BC. Accordingly, it is believed that the Assyrians were for some reasons not interested in the political and economic activities of nations around them at this period and consequently, this greatly aided the rise of kings Jeroboam II (Israel) and Uzziah (Judah) and the material prosperity that their nations witnessed (Eickmann, 2002). The ascension to the throne by Tiglah Pileser in 745BC, turned the fortunes of Assyria around. In 740/738 BC, he began his subjugation campaign and after the death of Jeroboam II (474), his son Zechariah who succeeded him, only reigned for six month before been killed by Shallum who himself reigned for only one month before been killed by Menahem in 745. Menahem of Samaria usurped the throne after the death of the last king of Jehu's dynasty (Macintosh, 1997, p. ixxxv). Menahem essentially, paid tribute to the Assyrian government led by Tiglah Pilezer as a means of sustaining his hold on the throne of the northern kingdom (cf. 2 Kings 15:19) (Constable, 2026). Sadly, between when Jeroboam II died and the fall of Samaria (722/721 BC), a succession of coups d'état took place which saw six different kings ascending the throne with four brutally assassinated (Constable, 2026). Hoshea was the last king before the fall of Samaria and he was like others, a puppet king. Tilah Pilezer eventually died in 727BC and Samaria fell shortly before Sargon II ascended the throne (Constable, 2026,). The political situation of the northern kingdom was precarious during the time of the prophet Hosea and it seems his career coincided mainly with the final years of the northern kingdom (Ceresko, 2009).

Literary Analysis of Hosea 8:4

i. The Hebrew Translation

הֵם הַמְּלִיכֹת וְלֹא מִמְּנֵי הַשִּׁירוּ וְלֹא יִדְעֵתִי כִּסְפָם וְזִהְיֶם עֲשׂוּ לָהֶם עֲצָבִים לְמַעַן יִפְרֹתוּ:

ii. English Translation

They have crowned kings without me; they have promoted officials without my knowledge. With their silver and gold they make idols for their own destruction

iii. Delimitation of Hosea 8:4

The text of Hosea 8:4 is part of the larger unit tagged Justice and worship, stretching from Hosea 4:1 to Hosea 8:14 (Leclerc, 2007). Specifically, it forms part of Hosea 8:1-14 which is a unit of its own and is termed Ephraim's Unfaithfulness (Leclerc, 2007). The opening words of chapter 8 "put the trumpet into your lip" is an exclamatory summons which signals a new unit (Nwaoru, 1999). Here, the prophet announces the coming of the eagle, which is a metaphor for 'enemy' (cf. Hosea 8:3), comes upon the house of the Lord because the people have rebelled against God and broken the laws. However, the text of study, Hosea 8:4, can be studied as a sub-unit of Hosea 8:1-14 when the opening word, *hēm* (they) which is not an emphatic pronoun but "introduces a circumstantial clause" (MacIntoch, 1997). Furthermore, the text is unique as a stand out unit when political and religious apostasies are linked together as two indissoluble crimes committed by the people. The wordings of Hosea 8:4, give it a distinct character to be studied as a unit. That is, words such as, kings and officials, silver and gold, give it a unique characteristic. Also, from the point of view of theme, it is a stand-alone unit. That is, it is an indictment of the people, an accusation based on political and religious apostasy.

Literary Genre of Hosea and Structure of Hosea 8:4

To understand the literary genre of Hosea 8:4, the entire book of Hosea and the style deployed by the prophet must be considered. That is, a holistic approach to the prophet's technique of writing should be understood. Generally, a study of the book, shows that it is a combination of prose and poetry and that it is often difficult to distinguish between both as they are fused together. In Hosea, "one element that strikes even a casual reader of the book of Hosea is its figurative language, consisting mainly of metaphors and similes. The two images appear with such frequency and intensity in the oracle that one will speak of Hosea as not only a prophet and poet, but a literary sculptor and artist" (Nwaoru, 1999, p.11). Thus, the book of Hosea is a poetry, couched in images and woven in metaphors

and similes (Nwaoru, 1999). Strictly speaking, chapters 1 and 3 are historical narratives while chapters 2, 4-14 are poetry. Constable considers the first three chapters to be narratives relating to the prophet's own experiences while the remaining parts are prophetic oracles (Constable, 2026). Within this style of the prophet, certain themes such as, religious apostasy, political apostasy, indictment, warnings, punishment, judgments etc. are elaborated. Consequently, the text of study, Hosea 8:4 is a historical narrative which announces God's indictment of Israel.

Concerning its structure, the text can be divided into two main parts which include:

1. Political Apostasy (Hosea 8:4a): They have crowned kings without my promptings and have promoted officials without my knowledge
2. Religious Apostasy (Hosea 8:4b): With their silver and gold they make idols For their own destruction

Analysis of the Text

1. Political Apostasy (Hosea 8:4a), They have crowned kings without me and have promoted officials without my knowledge

Hosea 8:4a raises the important question if the prophet in this context captures the contemporary situation of his time. It certainly appears that Hosea's thought captured the entirety of the Kingship in the Northern dynasty and when one puts into proper perspective the ascension to the Northern throne by Jeroboam 1 which was a revolt against the Davidic dynasty, the prophet might have completely repudiated the kingship of the Northern kingdom. In other words, regardless of the evidence in 1 Kings 9:1ff that established Jeroboam 1 as the first king of the Northern kingdom, the fact that Jehu through the prophet Elisha was anointed and commissioned, their sons and all who came after them, all of their reigns were schism. The argument here is that God can make use of anyone even a sinner to achieve or execute his decrees (Lang, Schaff, Schmoller, McCurdy, 2008). To show that the kingship of the Northern kingdom was not unacceptable, Macintosh (1997, p.299) asserts that, "Ahijah the Shilonite did not explicitly sanction the accession but merely predicted what will happen". Added to this act of schism is the adulterous kingdom that was also established.

Therefore, the rebels or ceassationists during the reign of king Rehoboam acted all by themselves and their action of setting up kings was not by or through the will or design of God whom they never consulted. Thus, “one example of Israel’s rebellion was the setting up of kings (Jeroboam 1 and his successors) and other leaders without consulting YHWH” (Constable, 2026, p.64). It becomes clear that Jeroboam 1 became king from self- will and not from God and also, he did not receive any form of instructions from God in relation to how he is to proceed as king. Consequently, Jeroboam 1 as soon as he became king and in other to establish his own kingdom, rebelled against God as he set up his own places of worship in the Northern Kingdom. Thus, he sinned against God and led Israel to sin as well.

Asher (27) in explaining the text of Hosea 8:4a argues that the prophet Hosea describes the illegitimacy of the kings of the Northern kingdom. That even though God promised Jeroboam 1, a dynasty of kings like the Davidic dynasty, the promise was dependent on Jeroboam’s faithfulness and dedication to the service of God as David did (cf. I Kings 11:37–38). However, Jeroboam failed in this regard. He turned aside after his own wisdom and forsook God. The result certainly was obvious and it manifested in the many civil unrest, violence and immorality that ensued after his death. This turbulence that characterized the Northern Kingdom, gave rise to political apostasy and this is captured in the following words:

Political apostasy is marked by treachery and deceit and by series of palace revolts. It is done in stupidity for apparent short-term advantage and its origin are found in human weakness. Kings and royal officials are promoted in rapid succession by the will of frail men and without any reference to God and the possibility of his initiative through his loyal servants (Macintosh, 1997, p. 298).

The two phrases *welo’ mimeni* (not by me) and *welo’ yade’eti* (without my knowledge), put the verse 4a into clear perspective. That is, the Prophet makes it clear that the actions taking place in the palace which lead to the coups and counter coups, bringing in new and different kings and the emergence of officials are not of God’s making. In concluding the analysis of Hosea 8:4a, it might be argued that the prophet Hosea in the immediate, was concerned about how the

government of the Northern kingdom was formed or constituted, a godless government, with incompetent officials and was a product of crude or raw brutality and bloodbath.

2. Religious Apostasy (Hosea 8:4b) “With their silver and gold they make idols for their own destruction”

It should be understood that the act of political apostasy coincided with the act of religious apostasy. That is, both forms of apostasies occurred side by side. They are mutually inclusive and linked together. Essentially, the exact same character that led them to political apostasy is responsible for religious perversion. The kingdom was at this time a very prosperous nation and as the text puts it, the wealth or material resources of the state was put into the project of religious idolatry.

The worship of idols, the servicing of syncretic cults where reckless self-indulgences of different kinds took place and was considered to be sign of plenty. Resources were not put into proper use but were wasted in adorning images and idols of worship which would be removed or destroyed. It is important to stress the fact that the word ‘idol’ is in plural (‘šabbîm) and this brings home the sense that the entire nation was filled with idols or statues used in many private sanctuaries in the nation (cf. Hosea 4:17; 13:2;14:9). Furthermore, the phrase ‘their destruction’, refers to those who crowned kings without God’s direction and set up royal offices all by themselves. Asher summarizes: “Idolatry was the means which these illegitimate kings used to establish and hold their power (cf. I Kings 12:26–33). The “they” that are cut off are the “they” who set up kings, made princes and made idols. This is national guilt resulting in a national penalty” (2024, p.27). The making of idols was a violation of the covenantal demands and principle between Israel and YHWH and the consequence of this, is the coming judgment of YHWH which Israel will not escape (cf. Hosea 8:1-7).

Hosea 8:4: An Exposition of Leadership Crisis in 8th Century Israel

Hosea 8:4 was a clear call by the prophet on Israel in relation to the complete collapse of leadership structure at that time. Indeed, this meltdown did not only show the political and religious tumult but also show that the people at this period were in great distress and pain. Significantly, the analysis of Hosea 8: 4 above

reveal massive leadership crisis and failure and the following provide a background for this crisis:

➤ Illegitimate Kings

The coming to power of kings not appointed by God and the subsequent assassinations or bloody coups and counter coups that followed the ascension of the throne but these different kings greatly destabilized political and religious leadership during this time. In specific terms, between when Jeroboam II died and the fall of Samaria (722/721 BC), a succession of coups d'état took place which saw six different kings ascending the throne with four brutally assassinated (Constable, 2026). Surely, what played out was raw power politics and not kingship through dynastic succession or prophetic anointing. No nation would thrive under such political upheaval and the consequences can only lead to the total collapse of the administrative framework of governance.

➤ Repudiation of the Covenantal Principle

The covenantal principle between YHWH and Israel was that Israel will remain faithful to YHWH and in turn, YHWH will be their God. By implication, YHWH will appoint kings through prophetic anointing hinged on dynastic succession and the king was to uphold the Law and lead the people to YHWH. However, during this period, the monarchy was far from being what it was designed to be. It was for the strongest and most brutal and not built on divine providence. Also, these kings completely abandoned YHWH for powerful nations while at the same time, worshipped the gods of these nations. Thus, Israel committed both religious and political idolatry. It is important to say that the consequence of Israel's apostasy was divine judgment and this was decisive. However, YHWH's judgment was not devoid of his mercy or love and in the words of Eickmann, "the distinctive note in Hosea is his portrayal of the God who loves when all possibility of loving has rightly ceased..." (2002, p.9). Thus, the judgment brought punishment upon Israel in the midst of YHWH's love.

➤ Perversion of Justice/ Failed State

Finally, Israel became a nation of injustice, oppression, corruption and sin. In other words, the covenantal demand that required Israel to be kind, good and loving to fellow Israelites was repudiated and the consequence was a society

characterized with evil and other forms of atrocities that undermined human dignity and brought misery, pain, hardship and death to follow Israelites. Thus, “the high-living rich exploited the poor. Merchants took dishonest profits. And money controlled the courts of law. Crowds filled the religious shrines, but the life of the people showed that their hearts were far from the Lord” (Eickmann, 2002, p.10). As would be expected, a nation with collapsed administrative governmental structure and lacking divine backing is surely destined to fail. Particularly, religious idolatry which became prevalent in 8th century Israel was a major sign that Israel had failed as a nation. Thus, state collapse was a direct consequence of leadership crisis. She abandoned YHWH for idol worship. Also, Israel’s foreign policies of aligning with Assyria and Egypt instead of trusting in YHWH’s power and benevolence to protect and provide for her showed failure in leadership. These nations especially Assyria finally destroyed Israel’s kingship and completely annihilated the nation Israel from history. The destruction of Israel marked the fulfillment of Hosea’s prophecies and Assyria was YHWH’s instrument or hand in carrying out the punishment of Israel on account of her irreligious actions

Leadership Crisis in the Context of Nigeria

Effective leadership is central for any form of meaningful development to take place in any nation. Leadership determines whether a nation moves forward economically, socially, politically, educationally and in all other areas that count when indicators for national growth and development are critically considered. Nigeria certainly can be said to be witnessing leadership crisis and this is true as she is failing in critical sectors that indicate development. Speaking about leadership, political leadership necessarily comes to mind and it is the sort of leadership that is saddled with the responsibility of governing a people and a nation or state. According to Ugwuozor, a leadership simply means “the ability to lead, direct and organize a group” (2021, p.52). That is, leadership involves a sort of social influence or guidance through which an individual guides, inspires and stimulates others to achieving a goal or target (Ugwuozor, 2021). In view of this, political leadership involves the ability to build a nation, state or society through the harnessing of available and scarce resources and appropriately channel these for the development of the nation and her inhabitants (Ugwuozor, 2021).

Sadly, political leadership in Nigeria appears not to be concerned with the effective management of available and scarce resources and this has led to serious developmental gap. “The discontent among Nigerians with the current state of affairs can be directly attributed to the loud calls for the polity and public policy to be redirected toward goals that could help improve the standard of living for the populace in all its aspects” (Mumuni, 2024). The failure of the political leadership has led to massive deficit in leadership and this is the foundation of the leadership crisis faced by Nigeria at present. Leadership crisis therefore is caused by the actions of politicians which is geared towards serving their interests alone and undermining good governance. Mumuni describes leadership crisis as:

Small class of political elites who are more concerned with actualizing their own self-interests than with advancing democracy. Government representatives impose unjustifiable, wasteful initiatives, suppress dissenting opinions, and undermine individual interests through harsh economic measures. As a result, there is widespread poverty and corruption (2024, p.90).

Achonu and Demian (2022), present a very interesting dimension to the discourse of leadership crisis in Nigeria. In studying family life in relationship to the formation of future political leaders, they argue that the pattern of ownership and sharing learned by children in many Nigerian families where the head takes the best part of everything is a major factor that instills the habit of selfishness, lack of accountability, corruption, self-serving mentality leading to abuse of power. Furthermore, leadership crisis is caused by poor, inexperienced, indiscipline and unprepared leadership which in itself is premised upon the lack of proper educational formation especially in the formative years of the child (Achonu and Demian, 2022). The consequence is manifested in bad decisions, weak governance leading to loss of public trust. Significantly, good and effective leadership would require character, virtue, adequate knowledge and sufficient training in governance and the opposite of these would lead to poor leadership. Therefore, “Leadership crisis in Nigeria is occasioned mainly by lack of intellectual training and discipline on the part of leaders of our national government” (Itodo and Onodugo, 2016, p. 109). Corruption is a major cause of leadership crisis and this is rooted in the distorted cultural and weak value system

that has taken over the society today (Itodo and Onodugo, 2016). The quest to remain in power or office and perpetrating all forms of undemocratic policies and actions greatly contribute too to leadership crisis and failure in Nigeria. Itodo and Onodugo provide a summary of this crisis as follows:

Bad leadership also arises from uncontrolled quest to remain in power and to enjoy outrageous salaries paid to Nigerian public office holders, most especially the executives and legislature. The major means of living in flamboyant affluence and conspicuous consumption in Nigeria is to hold a political office. Government functionaries in Nigeria often involve in several dubious means to amass dynastic wealth which their generation born and unborn cannot finish (2016, p.110).

Lastly, the saying that a people gets the kind of leadership they deserve is true in this context when one considers the docile nature of the citizenry in terms of participating effectively in determining those who get into political offices. Olagunju argues that it is a situation of cause and effect. That is, the citizenry are not proactive in terms of checkmating criminal and corrupt actions perpetrated by politicians, no positive and intentional criticism of the political class. The consequence is a small group of politicians who run riot, committing all forms of undemocratic actions leading to bad governance and loss of fate in the system.

Hosea 8:4 in the Context of Leadership Crisis in Nigeria

The narrative in Hosea 8:4 provides a better basis to consider leadership crisis in Nigeria. That is, Hosea 8:4 points to the dysfunctional procedures that characterize the emergence of leaders and the different shenanigans that surround leadership in general in Nigeria leading to massive failure in governance and plunging Nigerians into a state of hopelessness. The following therefore are some ways Hosea 8:4 helps to understanding leadership crisis in Nigeria.

➤ Criminal Leadership Selection Process

Hosea 8:4a speaks about the rise of kings to the throne through assassination, coups and counter coups leading to kings and leaders not qualified and approved by YHWH through dynastic successions. This mirrors the situation in Nigeria where leaders get into offices not because they were elected or the choice of the

people. Consequently, public good is undermined, governance suffers and the nation is crippled in all directions. A major factor that facilitates illegitimate leaders coming into office is electoral malpractice.

Electoral manipulation which is “the manipulation of electoral processes and outcomes so as to substitute personal or partisan benefits for the public interest” (Adeoti, 2022, p. 85). Granted that there are electoral irregularities that are occasioned by unconscious short coming emanating from electoral system, electoral malpractice in most cases has to do with the criminality involved in the organized and calculated act of subverting the will of the people through manipulation of the general electoral process and finally, the outcome of the election. The consequence of this is that persons who are not competent or have the best interest of the people end up in leadership position. Thus, it involves “all forms of wrong doing to truncate fairness in the electoral processes. It is usually aimed at giving unmerited favour to, or promoting the interest of a particular candidate or party” (Aliyu, Olawoyin and Bamidele, 2020, p.17). Such a candidate ordinarily is not popular among the electorate and probably not considered competent to lead. Electoral malpractices are usually inclusive or restrictive in nature. That is, inclusive when it involves all wrong doings that violate both international and local democratic tenets while it is restrictive when it involves violation of local democratic tenet. Consequently, electoral malpractices in Nigeria are usually both inclusive and restrictive. Therefore, just like crude power play was the mechanism for gaining leadership in 8th century Israel, impunity on the part of politicians, desperation and the drive to rule or lead by all means, undemocratic use of state power and lack of credibility on the part of electoral umpires, weak and manipulative electoral laws and primordial sentiments including religious and ethnic biases all contribute to electoral malpractices in Nigerian democratic space.

➤ **Idolatry of Wealth and Self-interest**

According to Hosea 8:4b, the political and religious elite that constituted the ruling class greatly deployed the resources of Israel to fund their worship of idols. It should be said that while idols and places where these were worshipped were built, the poor, weak of the society were neglected with no attention given to them and justice was perverted all through Israel. The above described situation can be

compared to what is obtainable in Nigeria where resources and wealth of the nation are exploited for the personal and selfish goals of politician. It appears that the blessings of abundant natural resources has become a curse to the nation and this is the case because the lives and situations of Nigerians do not show that they are a people blessed with abundance of resources. There is no accountability in terms of the management of these resources and this has led to massive opportunities for corruption to take place and the accumulation of generational wealth (Akpan, 2023). Speaking about corruption, the result of Transparency International on Corruption Perception Index 2025, showed that Nigeria scored 26 out of 100 and as such was ranked 142 out of 182 countries of the world (Ejalonibu, Ezenwajobi, and Udofa, 2026). Surely, corruption thrives because the leaders prioritize their selfish ambition and goal of looting public funds, mismanaging national resources instead of accountability and patriotic stewardship (Ejalonibu, Ezenwajobi, and Udofa, 2026). Commenting on the effects of corruption which is an effect of the idolatry of wealth and self-interest, Akpan writes:

Corruption induced by lack of accountability in our democratization process is deepening poverty. Corruption hinders the prospects of sustained economic development by impeding long-term growth and discouraging both foreign and local investment. This phenomenon fosters the occurrence of capital flight, inflation, and devaluation of the domestic currency (Akpan, 2023, p. 56).

Poor leadership selection process and the fact that a reasonable percentage of those who desire for public leadership and eventually get to these positions do not have the interests of the people at heart but seek only to satisfy their selfish interests continue to compound Nigeria's woes.

➤ State Collapse

Hosea 8:4 within the broader context of the entire book of Hosea speaks to the overall message of the prophet which was hinged on the failure and eventual destruction of Israel if she continued in the same political and religious trajectory. Regrettably, Israel remained adamant and in 720/721 BC, the state of Israel was

destroyed and ceased to exist. While the destruction of 8th century Israel can be tied to governance issues, internal sabotage cannot be overruled. This situation parallels the present situation of Nigeria as a nation. The poor and criminal electoral system of producing leaders and the selfish and incompetent leaders produced have led to massive institutional weakness and complete failure of administrative governance in some sectors of life in Nigeria. As a consequence, security has collapsed with insurgents and terrorists running riots in North-East, North-West and North-Central states of the country. Separatists agitators in the South-East causing mayhem, kidnappers, oil thieves, etc. making life difficult in the South-West and South-South respectively. Economically, the country is not doing well as she is today described as the poverty capital of the world (Brookings Institute, 2018). That is, over 87 million people lived below the poverty line and unfortunately, this has only increased that an estimated 129 million to 140 million people are said to be experiencing multidimensional poverty in Nigeria (Adedirun, 2026). This is even more sad with Nigeria having about 13% of the world's poor people (Adedirun, 2026). Citizens are traumatized with many groaning to pay bills with low minimum wage and in some cases, no jobs, etc. This situation has also increased the rate of emigration of Nigerians to other nations.

Effects of Leadership Crisis in Nigeria

The effect of leadership crisis in Nigeria cannot be over stated. Nigeria is on the brink and if the present crop of leaders do not change their governance trajectory or are not replaced with patriotic and competent leaders through legitimate democratic process, Nigeria might be heading to a point of political destruction. Ifeayin commenting on the nature of leadership failure in Nigeria writes:

Regrettably, Nigerian political leaders have failed in their main duty which is to assemble resources humanly and materially for development. Because of this, Nigeria at the moment battles with high rate of poverty, high level of unemployment, high rate of political instability, corruption, insecurity of lives and property and lack of infrastructural facilities in all sectors of the economy (2021, p.52).

It becomes clear that leadership crisis is at the root of the national crisis Nigeria is facing and this has affected development in all areas or sectors including social, economical and political developments. From independence, Nigeria has had the ill-luck of not having the best of leaders and one common denominator that defines these leaders and their regimes is corruption which over the years has been kept alive through humongous embezzlements and misappropriations of public funds (Ifeayin, 2021). Exploitation and personalization of state resources for the attainment of personal goals. The Trauma or strain caused by this, is inevitably seen in the underdevelopment of the nation in all ramification and the economic stagnation of her citizens (Mumuni, 2024). This point is aptly captured by Audu, Bello and Audu as follows:

Nigeria faces persistent challenges, including rising unemployment and deep socio-economic inequalities, which significantly hinder its development. Since the return to democratic governance in 1999, economic growth has been largely driven by oil revenues. Yet, this growth has been uneven, benefiting a privileged few while leaving the majority in economic hardship” (2025, p.87).

The above points are rooted in corruption which apart from being continuously fueled by poor leadership, is perpetrated in the acts of cronyism, ethnic and religious sentiments or nepotism leading to upholding of mediocrity over merit and intelligence. In addition, corruption as a major indicator of leadership crisis is practiced in Nigeria through, selective enforcement and application of the laws of the land, bribery and extortion of citizens by public officials, judicial manipulations, procurement irregularities, examination malpractice and use of fake documentations, state capture and use of state power to muscle citizens, lack of accountability and transparency, etc.

Leadership crisis is the cause of inefficiency in government which in turn allows for resource mismanagement. Furthermore, incompetency has paved the way for poor government policies and programs which are not in the best interest of the citizens in the long term. Policies or ideologies that are focused on giving aids or palliatives to citizens instead of creating job opportunities and providing necessary infrastructural projects that will encourage and support small businesses or Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) to grow and thrive. As can be seen all

around the country, many SMEs are closing down as it has become too difficult to keep their businesses running. The failure and inability to provide power, the high cost of living, the low purchasing power of the citizens thanks to the high rate of inflation are not only a manifestation of the ineptitude of the ruling government but a clear sign of leadership crisis. Added to the above is the housing problem in the country with many homeless citizens and many finding it difficult to pay rent. The country faces a 14.9 million housing deficit and there are no workable signs that there will be any positive improvement in this regard (The Guardian, 2026). Hunger is prevalent in the nation with over an estimated number of 34.7 million Nigerians are projected to face one form of food crisis or the other between June and August 2026 (Tene, 2025). The effect of leadership crisis gets worst when one considers the shameful fact that out of the N218bn capital project funds appropriated for the health sector of Nigeria, only N36 million representing 0.0165% of the total money was disbursed in 2025 (Vanguard, 2026). The implication of this is poor health sector for the country and this explains why health practitioners are constantly seeking opportunities to leave the country for other places with better working conditions. This sad revelation clearly shows how pitiable leadership crisis has gotten in Nigeria.

The effect of leadership crisis cannot be conclusively discussed without mentioning the issue of insecurity. The constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria states that the primary responsibility of the government is the protection of lives and property of the citizens. However, leadership crisis has made the contrary the case. That is, Nigeria is so insecure that the fear of been kidnapped by armed men who are either Fulani bandits, Boko-Haram elements, Unknown Gun Men, Islamic State of West Africa Province (ISWAP) or by a colleague or neighbour is palpable and causing a lot of citizens to be traumatized. It should be said that these armed groups emerged and grew to where they are today because of failure in leadership and the ineptitude of those in charge of the state's security. Also, the inability to use the state's resources and devise practical policies that would aid the development of the country thereby providing jobs, skills and better education for the large youthful population is a major contributor to the issue of insecurity. An idle mind surely can become a tool in the hand of the devil or persons who want to perpetrate violence and terrorism. These unemployed and in most cases unemployable youths have become tools for insecurity. The large farm

lands in the North which is the agricultural belt of Nigeria is completely deserted as farmers can no longer go to farm because of threats to their lives by terrorist organizations in the bushes and the ripple effect of this is food insecurity leading to hunger crisis in Nigeria.

Recommendations and Conclusion

This paper focused on leadership crisis and in doing so, Hosea 8:4 was critically studied with the view of providing a better understanding of leadership crisis, its causes and effects in the context of Nigeria. Interestingly, this paper established that the crisis of leadership in 8th century Israel during the time of the prophet Hosea is similar to the Nigerian experience especially in the areas of leadership selection, use of resources and generally accepted ethical or moral standards. Consequently, it is the case that leadership crisis or failure destroys a nation in totality and this is seen basically in the area of economy. This paper opens up the discussion on leadership in Nigeria and in Africa in general. It emphasizes the need for conscious policies that redefine and structure leadership in such a way that it achieves its purpose of organizing and structuring both human and natural resources for the development of the nation, development and empowerment of the citizens in all sectors of life and engender dignity, respect for the human person. As one would expect, a nation with failed economy would have a people or citizen that is impoverished, dejected and groaning in hopelessness. Also, leadership crisis makes it difficult to select or have the right and patriotic citizens to lead and the downside of this is that, persons who are either incompetent or filled with personal interests end up becoming leaders and everything about the nation continues to go down south. Just like ancient Israel, therefore, Nigeria and her citizens are groaning in bad leadership and the situation does not look like it will be remedied at any time soon. This paper therefore recommends that there must be critical reorientation of Nigerians and particularly leaders including those intending to serve. Such an orientation must be built on proper ethical and moral leadership standards and the need for patriotism as basis for leaders to emerge. Also, technical know-how or competence accompanied with sincere electoral process must become part of the system that produces leaders of the nation.

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